

Job Stressors and employees' Turnover Intention: The Moderating role of Personality Trait

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Abstract: *Climate Stressor refers to a physiological condition in which work-related duties and responsibilities become burdensome and overwhelming to the point that it imposes unhealthy effects on the mental and physical wellness of employees. This study focused on challenge stressors and hindrance stressors and its outcome on turnover intention. Challenge stressors are the type that require effort but benefits an employee's personal growth and achievement. Factors causing challenge stressors include job scope, responsibility, workload, and time pressure. While the hindrance stressors are work-related demands or circumstances that tend to constrain or interfere with an individual's achievements at work, and are not likely to be associated with potential gains for the individual. The purpose of the study is to find the impact of challenge stressors and hindrance stressors on turnover intention of the employees. The study was conducted on banking sector of Pakistan. For this purpose the data was collected from six banks of Pakistan including: Habib Bank Limited, National Bank of Pakistan, Meezan Bank, Bank Alfalah, MCB Bank, and United Bank Limited. Quantitative research design was applied by survey technique and the instrument of the study was questionnaire, comprise three sections along with characteristics of the sample. Results showed that, there is negative link between challenge stressors and hindrance stressors with turnover intention. Personality traits moderate the relationship between challenge stressors and hindrance stressors and turnover intention. It is concluded that hindrance stressors increases the chances of turnover intention in employees working in banks having Neuroticism and Conscientiousness personality. This research also opens new doors of research to explore the other type of stressors on turnover intention.*

Keywords: challenge stressors, hindrance stressors, turnover intention, personality types, moderation analysis

Introduction of the Study

The banking sector is one of Pakistan's economic foundations as it meets the financial needs of every sector of the nation. Stress has been observed among banking industry employees in recent years (Giao, 2020; Haque, 2021) as a result of

a number of factors, including an increase in workload (Navarro-Prados, 2024), changes in technology (Park & Shin, 2022), competitive challenges (Wen, 2020), excessive working hours (Yasin, 2021), lack of management support (Abbas, M., & Joshi, 2022), lack of authority (Ali, 2024), shortage of staff and resources (Babakus et al., 2017), an aggressive management style (Eckhardt et al., 2019), a lack of motivation (Feng, 2020), and organizational culture and policy (Bhutto & Aziz, 2018). Abbasi (2025) explained the stress as it has a negative impact on an organization's productivity, motivation, absenteeism, conflicts, and turnover intentions. So the current study focused on the stress that is experiencing by the workers in the banking sector. Research showed that in this modern era, every individual in this society is facing increasing level of stress, while the most crucial source of stress is their workplace (Altuntaş et al., 2022). Stress become common feature of work and can affect all aspects of an individual's life, including emotions, behavior, thinking ability, physical health and also turnover intention. The consequences of stress which includes psychological factors such as feelings of hopelessness are fatal and in many cases people tend quit the job (Chao et al., 2018; Chen & Fan, 2020).

DiPietro and Bufquin (2018) identified that stress caused by stressors that can be classified into two categories: challenge stressors (commonly positive in nature) and the hindrance stressors (which are negative in nature). The positive stressors help in learning opportunities, personal accomplishments, and growth (Kim & Ha, 2023; Memon & Sidat, 2024) are named as "challenge stressors". It means that they are beneficial for the individuals. Whereas, hindrance stressors, generally negative in nature creates job ambiguity, job insecurity and organizational politics (Tanveer, 2023). However, stressors that hinder an individual's ability to succeed at work and not likely to be accompanied with possible benefits for the individual are hindrance stressors (Yang, Ju & Lee, 2016).

Employee turnover intention is considered one of the utmost investigated topics in organizational behavior (Agarwal & Gupta, 2018). Many researchers reported that turnover intention is a critical issue and a major problem for organizations (Ariyabuddhiphongs & Marican, 2023; Bellou, Stylos & Rahimi, 2018). It can be defined as conscious wilfulness to leave the job and seek for alternative (Cohen, Blake & Goodman, 2019). However, Hopkins (2025) defined it as turnover intention is the feeling or thought of leaving the job but not essentially act of leaving the organization; it is viewed as a step before actual turnover. Turnover intention

negatively affects the performance of the organization by declining the overall quality, innovation and psychological wellness of employees who remain in the organization (Gumussoy, 2016).

Numerous scholars identified the link between stress and turnover intention (Kasa et al., 2022; Kwantes et al., 2023; Naidoo, 2023; Sundstrom et al., 2024) but no study have been found to identify the types of stressors (challenge stressors and hindrance stressors) and its effect on turnover intention in presence of personality as moderating variable. So this study aimed to find the link between stressors specifically challenge stressors and hindrance stressors) and turnover intention. The current research also explored the moderating role of personality between stressors and turnover intention.

2. Review of Literature

Stress is derived from the Latin term “Stingere” which literally meant to pull tight (Ucho, Mkavga, & Onyishi, 2024). In everyday sciences stress is seen as a worry alongside control which hinders employees to work at their best level (Akgunduz, Adan and Alkan, 2019). However, stress is a reaction of human body when it experiences any change which could be physical, mental, or emotional strain or tension (Albrecht & Marty, 2017). Antwi et al. (2018) stated that there is always a stressor which causes tension, from a good or bad situation, which enables stress. Gumussoy (2020) reported that stress is a condition that is built-in which usually occurs when individuals have to face some kind of threat. When individual faces stress, his psychological health also suffered that lead to prevent from achieving the organizational objectives (Kim & Back, 2019).

2.1 Challenge Stressors and Turnover Intention

Saeed et al. (2023) identified that there are some positive stressors known as challenge stressors which help an individual in his own growth and achievement and requires efforts. The challenge stressors are more positive and result of time pressure, job scope, responsibility, and workload. However, Ng and Stanton (2023) illustrated that challenge stressors are helpful and beneficial for the employees as well as the organization. For example: responsibility and workload regard to be challenge stressors (Yunfan et al., 2025), are encouraged by employees as it

enhances their growth and also motivates them to achieve their tasks (Zahra, Khan & Ijaz, 2025). Literature showed the inverse relationship between growth, motivation and absenteeism (Zimmerman, 2020). There is also association between challenge stressors and job satisfaction and the performance of employees but challenge stressors have negative relationship with turnover intentions (Yang, 2015). Van Den Heuvel et al. (2025) also found that challenging job demands had negative relationship with turnover intentions. When the impact of challenge stressors gets strengthen, the effect of turnover intentions gets reduced (Li & Zhang, 2024).

It was revealed that challenge stressors and job attitudes has positive relationship (Hu et al., 2025). Employees believe that when they face challenge stressors they would overcome that stress successfully which would lead them to high personal growth and achievement (Frieder, Wang & Hu, 2018). These challenge stressors boost up the confidence of employees which helps them to actively solve the problems through hard work as it gives the sense of achievement (Chowdhury & Sahoo, 2021). Worker's high engagement and motivation to the achievement is the result of challenge stressors (Arnold, Fletcher & Daniels, 2017). High level workload, time constraints, new interests and measure of commitment are fall in the category of challenge stressors (Arasli et al., 2022). These challenge stressors make workers to feel that they are fit for managing their work. However, challenge stressors are the source of inspiration as employees' trust that their more valuable input will bring higher accomplishment (Abbas & Joshi, 2020). Moreover, it can help employees to reduce stress and encounter challenges in a positive manner (Cohen et al., 2019). The employees who are engaged in challenge stressors, experience positive emotions and they put their all efforts to achieve the job requirements (Giao, 2020). A study indicated that challenge stressor is positively linked with job engagements (Hopkins, 2025). The challenge-related stressors, was made up of things representing job scope, time pressure, high levels of workload, and obligation. Workers continued to see these job requirements as posing a challenge and providing opportunities for personal development and accomplishment. These discussion lead to hypothesize that:

H1: Challenge stressors linked with turnover intention in banking sector of Pakistan.

2.2 Hindrance stressors and Turnover Intention

Previously, Hu et al. (2025) identified that If a person faces some kind of barriers

which does not let him progress to his goals and achievements then he is coming across “negative stress” which is also known as “hindrance stressors”. Moreover, Jeswani and Dave (2022) stated that the reasons behind these stressors could be job ambiguity, job insecurity or organizational politics. Hindrance stressors caused decreased job satisfaction, lower commitment to work, low level performance, more intentions for turnover and also job withdrawal (Joo, Hahn & Peterson, 2021). Role ambiguity and conflict is considered to be hindrance stressors (Kwantes et al., 2023; Tanveer, 2023). Van Den Heuvel et al. (2025) discovered that these types of workplace stressors are negatively linked with performance. While Yasin (2021) described that there is very limited time to perform a given task is hindrance stressor. According to previous research, hindrance stressors linked to psychological or physiological costs and negative influence on performance and motivation (Wu et al., 2020). Studies found that hindrance stressors have damaging symptoms, especially mental health at workplace (Ucho et al., 2024). When workers are confronted with threatening demands, they can develop a psychosomatic illness that leads to depression (Sundstrom et al., 2024). The organisational environment, workers' capacity, role clash, job calculating, role burden, overtime, job diffidence, and so on are all causes of hindrance stressors (Saeed et al., 2023). Hindrance stressors are universally regarded as negative and have a negative impact on employee morale, workplace attitudes (i.e. organizational promise, job happiness), efficiency (Park & Shin, 2022) and personal growth (Naidoo, 2023). While more, it is positively linked with anxiety and discomfort (Memon & Sidat, 2024).

A study was conducted in Pakistan on job ambiguity, workload, role conflict, and resource inadequacy (Haque, 2021). Results showed that hindrance stressors positively correlated with turnover intentions and absenteeism, and inversely correlated with work performance. Various studies suggested that the impact of hindrance stressors on desirable job outcomes is negative (Babakus, Yavas & Karatepe, 2017; Frieder, Wang & Hu, 2018; Chowdhur & Sahoo, 2021). Arnold, Fletcher and Daniels (2017) also mentioned that hindrance stressors increase turnover cognition, and decreases job performance. It is stated that hindrance stressors lower the level of motivation of employees (Antwi et al., 2018). Furthermore, hindrance stressors do not let the employees have that belief of success and they have a feeling of failure (Ariyabuddhiphongs & Marican, 2023). So

eventually they would think of quitting their job. These hindrance stressors would make an employee believe that they will not be able to reach his goal; he will worry due to this reason which further would lead to distracted behavior (Altuntaş et al., 2022). Studies showed that anxiety faced by employees is predicted when the hindrance stressors are interacted with control and support (Albrecht & Marty, 2017). Demotivation in employees is created by hindrance stressors, as they believe that they cannot cope up with the stress (Arasli et al., 2022). The growth and future gains of employees are obstructed by hindrance stressors, so they endure negative psychological reaction (DiPietro & Bufquin, 2018). Based on this discussion, it can be hypothesized that:

H2: Hindrance stressors linked with turnover intention in banking sector of Pakistan.

2.3 Personality Trait as Moderating Variable

Numerous studies have been conducted to explore the relationship between personality trait and turnover intention (Kim, 2020). Harari et al. (2024) discovered that people's turnover intentions and behaviors are influenced by their personality attributes. Another research by Marchalina (2022) highlighted those employees' intentions to leave the job predicted by the characteristic of emotional stability, whereas decisions to actually leave were predicted by the traits of conscientiousness and agreeableness. The results indicated that employees who are low on Emotional Stability may intend to quit while individuals who are low on Agreeableness or high on Openness may engage in unplanned quitting. In order to determine the key influences of personality on turnover intentions in India, McCormick et al. (2024) conducted a study. According to the findings, extraversion and agreeableness both have a significant negative impact on turnover intention. Numerous studies have revealed that employees are more likely to consider leaving their jobs when they are under more stress (Li & Zhang, 2024; Naidoo, 2023; Widiger et al., 2023). A positive relationship was also found between work-life conflict, stress, and turnover intentions by Zimmerman (2020).

A research by Van Den Heuvel et al. (2025) reported that an employee may want to leave their job voluntarily and involuntarily based on its job consequence and his perception about the job. They also added that voluntary turnover is considered to be employee's decision to quit the organization even when an organization wants them

to retain Whereas, involuntary turnover occurs when the employee is released by the organization, even if the employee doesn't want to leave there job. Widiger et al. (2023) illustrated that. Voluntary turnover involves resigning or quitting, while involuntary turnover is allied with layoffs, retirement, dismissals and death. In literature, the researcher shows more interest towards the voluntary turnover to assess the process and thought of employee go through before quitting from their job and to understand why they want to leave their organization (Yang, Ju & Lee, 2016).

Turnover intention encompasses the employee evaluation and perception of alternative jobs (Yang, Ju & Lee, 2016). Employees quit for several reasons, i.e. some are more focusing on their career goals and some avoid negative working conditions and other looking for the opportunities that are more monetarily attractive (Zahra et al., 2025). Park and Shin (2022) listed four components related to the turnover intention model, which included (1) an employee's having a plan to leave, (2) leaving without plan regarding what to do next because of a negative event, (3) leaving the organization with an alternative job search plan and (4) leaving the organization because of dissatisfaction. Studies also revealed that there is association between stress and personality types (Gumussoy, 2020).

According to the previous research, personality traits are linked with stress (Frieder et al., 2018). Some of the the traits help to cope with the stress at workplace such as Extraversion and Agreeableness while other are associated positively with stress including Neuroticism and Openness. Although stress and personality are important concept in behavior organization (Sundstrom et al., 2024), but the effect may effect on the context and culture of the organization. A research reported that extraversion personality help to reduce the stress at workplace, Neuroticism showed the similar results (Widiger et al., 2023), agreeableness showed the inverse link with stress at workplace. Conscientiousness personality trait positive increase with stress and openness to experience showed negative association with stressors at workplace (Abbas & Joshi, 2022).

A study by Altuntaş et al. (2022) conducted to find the link between five personality traits and turnover intention. They reported that there is positive link between conscientiousness, and neuroticism and turnover intention. While more, increase in Agreeableness and openness will lead to decrease in turnover intention. Similar results were also discussed by Bellou, Stylos & Rahimi (2018) and Eckhardt et al.

(2019). They illustrated the positive relationship between two of personality traits (neuroticism and conscientiousness) and negative link with openness, Agreeableness and extraversion.

These details help to hypothesize the link between stressors, turnover intention and personality trait:

H3: Personality trait moderate the relationship between stressors and turnover intention

2.4 Theory Underpinning the Study

The challenge-hindrane framework and the transactional stress theory have some similarities (Chowdhury & Sahoo, 2021). The stress of the employees is raised when employee encounter with long work hours , shift of work which are not quite flexible and when there is work-family conflict (Eckhardt et al., 2019; Harari et al., 2024). Both hindrance and challenge stressors optimistically correlate through the development of stress symptoms (McCormick et al., 2024). This study also supported by traditional Turnover Theory, reported by Naidoo (2023) and also mentioned by Li and Zhang (2024). Traditional Turnover Theory supported the concept of stress and turnover intention among the employees. According to this theory employee focus on the conditions and market alternatives before quitting the job. They illustrated the new opportunity and compare it with the stress they are facing at their current workplace (Julyan & Prawitowati, 2025; Farhan & putri, 2024). This intention belongs to psychological trait, experience dissatisfaction with job, work life balance and evaluation of the nature of job in cultural context. This research model also supported by Trait Theory of Personality. According to this theory, stress and turnover intentions logically linked with personal traits of the employees. It was modified by Kasa et al. (2022) and applied by many researchers in their researches. Kim (2020) reported that employees' turnover intention based on their stable personality traits across different situations. They take decision based on their behaviors which is formed by their personality attributes (Jeswani & Dave, 2022). So the following Conceptual framework of the current study also supported by the previous theories of organizational behavior.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1 Conceptual framework

3. Research Methodology

Research methodology should base on the study's goal and research questions (Hair et al., 2017). This research applied positivism philosophy as the research based on description of the details based on data and its results. Furthermore this study is descriptive by nature. The current study used deductive research approach to develop the hypothesis, test the hypothesis and conclude the results. Furthermore the current research testing the existing theory. The research strategy is survey method and quantitative research design is applied in this research. This study is cross sectional by time frame as the data is collected once and tested it.

3.1 Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

Population of the study is employees at administrative level (branch manager, operations managers, cash management officers, cheque processing officers, marketing services managers, loan officers, financial services officers, and compliance officers) working in different types of banks in Pakistan. The selection of the banking sector is justified as they face different kinds of stresses at their workplace at daily basis. Meanwhile high turnover intention is also recorded in banking sector due to its stressed environment (as suggested by Navarro-Prados, 2024 and Tanveer, 2023). The ratio of turnover in banking sector is high as compare to other professions (Yasin, 2021), so the current research explores different stressors that linked with the turnover intention of the bankers. Sample of the

research means subset of the population having similar characteristics (Hair et al., 2017). So the sample is selected from six banks of Quetta including: National Bank of Pakistan., Bank Alfalah, Habib Bank limited, Meezan bank, MCB bank and United Bank limited. The sample size is 230 managers at different departments selected conveniently. The sample size is based on recommendations of Cooper (2020) and Williams, Wiggins & Vogt (2021) for moderation analysis. Data was collected by self-administrative questionnaire having three sections of variables (stressors, turnover intention, and personality trait) items along with demographic details of the respondents.

3.2 Research Instrument

Cavanaugh (2000) used an 11-item scale to assess hindrance and challenge stressors, which included 5 hindrance stressors items and 6 challenge stressors items, also utilized by Hopkins (2025). On a scale of 1 (no stress) to 5 (extreme stress), the participants were asked to rate how stressful the statements were at work. “The amount of work that must be completed in the selected time.” and “The failure to adequately grasp what is required of me on the job.” are two examples of questions. Ten-Item Personality Inventory (Gosling et al., (2003) and 13-item instrument of Turnover Intention Scale by Camman et al. (1979) and modified by Gumussoy (2020), were utilized in this study. Turnover intention scale was also used by Bothma and Roodt (2013) and Taboli (2015). The sample items of the scale are “To what extent is your current job satisfying your personal needs?” and “How often you are frustrated when not given the opportunity at work to achieve your personal work-related goals?” The study was conducted from septemmmber 2025 to December 2025 and data was tested by statistical methods.

3.3 Ethical Considerations

This research study committed to upholding all the ethical standards of research. The respondents were treated with respect, and participation was on voluntary bases. The letter of consent was attached to a questionnaire in order to give detail regarding the purpose and process of the research study. The letter attached also includes confidentiality to be protected. The participation was given the option to withdraw from the study at any time. The individual participants had been shade with confidentiality during the reporting process. The questionnaire collected personally by hand (70%) and online by using Google forms (30%). The score of individual

aggregated and participant demographics not linked with their organization. All the raw data were secured from public view. The research was having no personal interest or gain (monetary, professional or personal) to conduct the study in the institution.

3.4 Statistical/ Data Analysis Tools

Before testing the hypothesis, all variables have been entered in SPSS (statistical package for social sciences, Version 24). SPSS is a statistical programme that aids to organise, analyse and interpretation of survey data (Lamprianou, 2024). SPSS software helped to analyse the relationship between the variables, impact of independent variables on dependent variables, confirmatory factor analysis and assessing which items captures the intended constructs. The macro bootstrap technique was used to analyse (moderation hypothesis), it is one of the powerful method for analysing the interaction effects (Hair et al., 2020). A bootstrap analysis is a nonparametric approach, making no assumptions about the variables' sampling distribution or indirect effects. Moreover, this can applied to small and moderate samples with more confidence (Preacher & Hayes, 2007; Lamprianou, 2024).

4. Results of the Study

This study was conducted to find the relationship between stressors, turnover intention and personality trait. Several tests applied to attain the research objectives including: normality of the data, correlation between the variables, factor analysis, Consistency analysis and Moderation analysis by Process Marco. Data coding, outlier detection, missing value detection in the data set (Multivariate and Univariate), and normality assessment (Shapiro-wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests) was also applied.

4.1 Data screening

Data screening involve normality checking, missing value and outlier's detection of the data. Data was coded twice as first coding was done when the research scale was design from 1 to 5 points for collection of responses. Secondly, data was coded when entered into the software. Normality of the data assessed by Shapiro-wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests and found that the data is normal for further procedure.

The value of Shapiro-wilk was less than .05 and Kolmogorov-Smirnov value was greater than 0.20 (data considered from normal distributed). Missing value was not found in data and there was also no issue of outliers in data. So data proceeded to reliability and validity test.

4.2 Validity and Reliability

In order to determine the individual item's reliability, the construct inner reliability, the composite's reliability, as well as discriminant validity, Convergent Validity, and Content Validity, are determined. Thus, in order to achieve quality in the final result of the research, both reliability and validity are assessed. The level, to which assessments are free of common errors and biases, as well as the Give-up Constant Outcomes, is defined as reliability (Turner, Cardinal & Burton, 2017). Similarly, Tobi and Kampen (2018) illustrated that instrument reliability and errors are inextricably linked, and as a result, when the error is so small, it increases instrument reliability. The ultimate goal of reliability is to reduce errors and bias from the study (Shymko, 2018). In this study, the average variance for each question is extracted, and the composite reliability is verified. According to Liao and Hitchcock (2018) the AVE should be equal to or greater than the value of 0.05. These commonly accepted values are used in this study to demonstrate the capability of items whose average variance is extracted, Cranach's alpha, and composite reliability are explained. Alpha coefficient was .86 for turnover intention; personality trait (.89), hindrance stressors (.78) and challenge stressors was 0.85, respectively.

Table 4.1 Reliability Statistics (N=265)

Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach Alpha (α)
Challenge Stressors	05	0.852
Hindrance Stressors	06	0.783
Turnover intention	13	0.866
Personality Trait	10	0.898

The Cronbach's Alpha results for every variable are according to the suggestion of hair et al. (2010). For challenge stressors the Cronbach Alpha was 0.852. Hindrance stressors had a total value of 0.783. Personality trait is moderator in this research had

10 items with a Cronbach alpha of 0.898. Turnover intention which is a dependent variable has 13 items with a Cronbach alpha of 0.866. If the value is greater than 0.550, it is satisfactory (William 2006).

Factor analysis was conducted to measure the validity of the scale and each item. If items are fine and exhibiting variables, then it is called construct validity, but Bagozzi and Yi (1988) reported that construct validity is an essential requirement to analyse the presumptions. In this present study, findings achieved by the model fit goodness presents the whole validity of the construct. Fornell and Larcker (1981) standard applied to determine discriminant validity. They proposed that to determine discriminant validity, latent variables' association should be above the AVE's square root. According to Williams, Wiggins and Vogt (2021), the value of the association between factors must be less than .85. Several items have to be used to measure every variable in the measurement model (Harari et al., 2024). To measure the validity, every construct must contain at least three items. To follow the above-mentioned procedure that Kline (2005) preferred, two major reasons are as follows. The loaded value of each factor must be greater than .40 (Hair, 2017). Whereas for identifying the correlation between items, the value must be less than .85 (Kline, 2005). The final results of factor loading showed that all the items are appropriate for further analysis.

4.3 Demographic analysis

After reliability and validity analysis, the next step of analysis was to measure the demographic characteristics of the respondents. It helps to identify the diversity of the respondents for generalizability of the findings.

Table 4.2 Demographic analysis

characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	159	65.0
Female	116	35.0
Total	265	100.0
Age		

20-30	110	33.3
31-40	96	40.0
41-50	47	13.3
Above 50	22	13.3
Total	265	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	71	23.3
Married	194	76.6
Total	265	100.0
<hr/>		
Income Level		
Less than 50,000	72	30.0
50,000-100,000	96	31.7
100,000-200,000	48	20.0
200,000-300,000	44	18.3
Total	265	100.0
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For collection of data 300 questionnaires distributed to the selected sample. Then this study got feedback from 265 respondents. The table shows 159 male participants in the observation that shows 65% of the population size. Separately from this, 116 female participants in the observation that makes up 35% of the study size. The above table depicts that the respondents between ages 20-30 are 33.3%. Those between ages 31-40 are 40%, respondents between ages 41-50 are 13.3 % and those above 50 are 13.3%. The above table shows that 71 respondents were single which makes up 23.3% of the sample size and 194 respondents were inclusive which makes up 76.6% total study size. The study depicts salaries that are lesser than 50000 were 72 that form almost 30% of total sample population. The ones with having salaries ranging from 50000 to 100000 were 96 that form up 31.7% of the sample size. The ones with salaries ranging between 100000 to 200000 were 48 which make up 20% of population frame and those with salaries that are between 200000-300000 were again of the amount 44 which form 18.3% of the population study size of the study.

4.4 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive analysis helps to explain the central value of the variables and its deviation from the central point. Skewness and kurtosis shows the value is greater

than 0.05.

Table 4.3 Descriptive Statistics

	M	S.D	Skewness	Kurtosis
Challenge Stressors	3.6733	.61552	-.690	1.033
Hindrance Stressors	3.5667	.61028	-.126	-.095
Turnover intention	3.8417	.43142	-.295	-.230
Personality	2.4817	.53520	.365	-.747

Mean value of Challenge Stressors 3.63733 along a standard deviation 0.615. Hindrance Stressors the results are 3.566 and 0.610 S.D. respectively. The mean result of Turnover intention was 3.8417 with a standard deviation of 0.431 and for Personality Trait the values were 2.4817 and 0.535 S.D. respectively. The variables are within the acceptable ranges i.e. (-1 to +1) and (-3 to +3) which means that the data is suitable and appropriate for regression analysis.

4.5 Correlation Analysis

The correlation calculation is conducted to see if there are any relationships between the variables. It also provides information on the direction of the link between the variables. Researcher is quantitative in nature for which correlation analysis is frequently used to determine the associations among the variables. It reflects about directions in the relationship among the variables.

Table 4.4 Correlation between the Variables

	CS	HS	TI	PT
CS	1			
HS	-.395**	1		
TI	-.312**	.495**	1	

** . Correlation value is significant for the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The association among Challenge Stressors and Personality Trait has a magnitude of 0.277 but weak in nature with a positive direction. The association among the Hindrance Stressors and turnover intention is highly significant with a magnitude of .485 and has a moderate correlation with a positive direction. The association among Challenge Stressors as well as turnover intention is significant enough with a magnitude of -.312 but weak to moderate in nature with a negative direction. The association between Hindrance Stressors and turnover intention is highly significant with a degree of .495. Along with positive direction but moderate in nature.

4.6 Hypothesis Results

The current research was consisted of four main hypotheses and twelve sub-hypotheses. Dependent variable for the study was turnover intention; independent variable was challenge and hindrance stressors, while the moderating variable was personality with its five dimensions (Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Open to Experience, Neuroticism and Conscientiousness).

The first hypothesis of the study was to find the impact of challenge stressors on turnover intention. Result showed that challenge stressors 32% predict the turnover intention with negative beta value (-.021, and $p=0.00$). Results showed that challenge stressors are predictor of turnover intention. Second hypothesis of the study was to find the impact of hindrance stressors on turnover intention. Results showed that hindrance stressors impact 41%. The beta value is significant at 0.000 ($b=.793$). Third hypothesis of the study was related with the five personality traits as a moderator between challenge stressors and turnover intention. The results are reported below:

4.7 Moderation Analysis

Moderation analysis help to identify the interaction effect of five personality traits (Extraversion, Agreeableness, Open to Experience, Neuroticism and Conscientiousness) on challenge stressors and turnover intention. PT1 to PT5 is five types of personality trait and its interaction with challenge stressors to predict the effect of turnover intention.

Table 4.5 Moderation Analysis of Challenge Stressor

	Co-eff	Se	T	P	LLCI	ULCI	R ²	F
Turnover Intention								
Personality Trait	-2.6994	.6798	-3.9707	.0001	-4.0387	-1.3601		
Challenge Stressors	-2.0752	.6866	-4.0224	.0028	-3.4279	-.7226		
PT1*CS	.517	.1765	2.929	.000	.159	.8621	.4109	54.701
PT2*CS	.345	.0251	5.245	.020	.165	.6141	.129	38.612
PT3*CS	.278	.1675	4.657	.003	.121	1.320	.372	81.210
PT4*CS	.622	.0313	6.373	.000	.219	.7123	.118	121.61
PT5*CS	.548	.0705	4.580	.008	.142	1.460	.083	51.120

Relationship between challenge stressors and turnover intention predicted with personality trait as showed in table. This shows model has a power of 41.09% ($R^2 = .4109$). R denotes that the independent variable and moderator predict the dependant variable (turnover intention). The model also has a fitness value (F) greater than 2.6 with a p value significant at 0.05 that the model is fit for the data. As the coefficient values estimated by regression in the model, personality trait, Challenge Stressors and Int_1 to Int_5 are significant at 95% confidence interval One-unit increase in Challenge Stressors would cause a 2.0752 unit decrease in turnover intention. So, the hypotheses of moderating effect of personality trait accepted.

Secondly, the model was tested as effect of hindrance stressors on turnover intention with moderating effect of five personality traits (Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Open to Experience, Neuroticism and Conscientiousness).

Table 4.6 Moderation Analysis of Hindrance Stressor

	Co-eff	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI	R ²	F
Turnover Intention								

Personality Trait	-2.4538	.4273	-5.7426	.000	-3.2956	-1.6120		
Hindrance Stressors	-2.0930	.4366	-4.7936	.000	-2.9531	-1.2328		
PT1*HS	.497	.193	4.345	.000	.281	2.221	.268	61.608
PT2*HS	.704	.246	6.410	.0008	.127	4.741	.153	101.04
PT3*HS	.368	.464	4.364	.003	1.181	6.025	.324	92.012
PT4*HS	.061	.681	7.820	.000	2.721	3.931	.109	61.421
PT5*HS	.572	.252	5.201	.000	3.512	4.012	.390	34.472

The above table depicts the results of moderation effect of personality on hindrance stressors and turnover intention. It shows that the model has a prediction power of greater than 10% ($R^2 = .10$). It indicates that hindrance stressors create variance in the dependent variable (turnover intention) showed by the model. The model also has a fitness value (F) greater than 2.65 with a p value of 0.000 which indicates that the model is acceptable for the data. As the coefficient values estimated by model of regression, personality, Hindrance Stressors and Int_1 are significant at 95% confidence interval. A one-unit increase in Hindrance Stressors would cause a 2.093 unit decrease in turnover intention. So, hypothesis, which states that the Hindrance Stressors have a positive affiliation with turnover intention accepted.

5. Discussion

According to the findings of first hypothesis, there is a negative association between challenge stressors and turnover intention. The hypothesis accepted as the results showed that turnover intention and challenge stressors have a negative association in Banking sector. Results also revealed that when the challenge stressors intensity is high the turnover intention notably is low. These findings are consistent with previous results of Hu et al. (2025). They reported that challenge stressors are always positive and the outcome of time pressure, workload, Responsibility and also job scope. Findings of the current study also match the findings of Joo, Hahn and

Peterson (2021) as the challenge stressors have a negative association with leaving to the organization. The challenged stressor have been taken positive, dealing with stressors posed by challenges can be motivational and offer opportunities for individual development and knowledge at workplace as mentioned by Li and Zhang (2024) and Naidoo (2023). These results are also in line with the previous outcomes of the Saeed et al. (2023), illustrated that workplace challenge stressors have an inverse impact on worker intentions to leave the organization.

Results of the current study showed that hindrance stressors are perceived as barrier to achieve the organizational goals and target accomplishment. Previously Tanveer (2023) also said that when employees faced constraints or competing job demands, people can take shortcuts, reducing their effort to the point that they only meet the bare minimum for specific tasks, or even abandoning them entirely. So there is positively correlation between hindrance stressors and turnover intention. These results also in line with the finding of Wen (2020) as hindrance stressors are linked to increase the leaving intentions. The third hypothesis of the current study was to explore the moderating effect of personality traits on the relationship between stressors and turnover intention. The findings of stressors with personality types showed that strong personality lead to accept the stress of job and work for the organization. Extraversion personality types with challenge stressors showed they cope with challenge stressors and minor effect is reflected on turnover intention while results also showed that the interaction of challenge stressors with extraversion personality have strong negative effect on turnover intention. Results of Agreeableness with stressors showed that there is negative link between these variables in presence of agreeableness trait of personality. Results also showed that neuroticism increases the stressor and increases the intention to leave the job. According to the findings, conscientiousness and Open to Experience showed ability to cope with the stress and reduces the turnover intention. Previously, Li et al. (2015) also reported the similar findings. However, Yang, Ju and Lee (2016) results are also consistent with these findings.

These results also in line with the previous results of researchers (Abbasi, 2025; Babakus, Yavas & Karatepe 2017; Chao et al., 2018, Cohen, Blake & Goodman, 2019). Similarly, extraversion personality types with hindrance stressors showed

they cope with challenge stressors and strong effect on turnover intention while results also showed that the interaction of hindrance stressors with extraversion personality have strong positive effect on turnover intention. Results of Agreeableness with stressors showed that there is positive link between these variables in presence of agreeableness trait of personality. Results also showed that neuroticism increases the stressor and increases the intention to leave the job. According to the findings, conscientiousness and Open to Experience showed ability to cope with the stress and reduces the turnover intention. Results by Frieder, Wang and Oh (2019) showed the similar results as stressors with personality have strong positive impact on turnover intention.

6. Conclusion

This research aimed to explore the relationship between different type of stressors and turnover intentions in banking sector of Pakistan. While more the current research also identified the moderating role of personality trait on stressors and turnover intention. Based on these results it can be concluded that there are two type of stressors challenge and hindrance stressors. This study concluded that increase in challenge stressors leads to reduce the turnover intention. Hindrance stressors are negative in nature and promote the turnover intention. .ba This study concluded that, it is necessary for businesses to retain a thriving workforce that is energized to grow and expand in order to maintain stress and remain sustainable. Stressors are an important part of the workplace and the type of stressors tells whether the stress is positive in nature or negative. It is also found that for every individual the level of these stressors differed based on their personality. Whereas workload was seen as both; challenge as well hindrance stressors. It can be concluded that a stressor which is a challenge in one occupation might be a hindrance in another profession. It is more important to know about the outcome of these stressors rather to investigate upon the level of challenge-hindrance stressors in each individual. It is suggested that managing challenge stressors can be time-consuming and stressful consequently results in decrease of turnover intention.

6.1 Theoretical Implication

The study contributes several theoretical implications. The current study extends the

work of De Hoogh and Den Hartog (2008). Only a few studies examined the type of stressors and its role in organizational setting in Pakistan. Since no study has yet examined the negative and positive stressors, the current study will extend the literature of these variables and highlight the importance of stressors on employees' and organizational outcomes. The study showed that challenge stressors leads to low turnover intention and hindrance stressors showed positive attitude towards turnover intention. This study provides a new research framework to add in literature of organizational behaviour.

6.2 Practical Implication

This study contributes to several practical implications. One relates to the selection of employees should base on their personality type. Employees with strong personality and ability to manage the stress shall be selected. The finding of the study suggests positive stressors increase the ability to perform the task at workplace as compared to daily routine work. Thus, organizations should pay a specific attention to development of positive challenging stressors. This may be developed by encouraging training and rewards system in the organization and develop performance standard. This may also help to minimize turnover intention in an organization. It is suggested, organizations which hope to reduce the stress of employees needs to enhance the control of workers and social support when facing with hindrance stressors e.g. conflict with other workers and the politics prevailing inside the organization. The study suggest management should adopt appropriate strategies and enhance human resource practices that lead to positive personality traits which lead to increased retention of employees.

6.3 Limitations and Further Recommendations of the Study

Some of the important limitations faced by this study that can be address in future are mentioned as: First, the model of the current study based on negative outcome of the organization. Other types of stressors can be explored and tested on positive outcomes of the organization. Secondly, the population was limited to the administrative level of banking sector. Further study can be investigated from other professions and participants from different context to determine whether the results are similar or differ from this study. Third, the self-rated scale was used to tests the personality, stressors and turnover intention, this measurement scale may lead to

self-biased results. The respondents in self-rated questionnaire may rate themselves more favourable. Beside the literature has also support the facts of self-rated response is effective to measure authenticity, the further study can be done by two diverse groups as leaders and subordinates can rate each other rather than to self-assessing.

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